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The Engineer; The Oblivious Prostitute?

Collins Dictionary, 3rd sense of the word

Bill Kinlough

A philosophical View of Engineering Thinking and curricula

"Now I am become death, the destroyer of worlds"

Oppenheimer's words after completion of the project"

Whether one considers this diligence of Oppenheimer's to be evidence of moral weakness or of admirable strength largely defines one's view of the moral responsibility of scientists and political men

Editor *The New Atlantis*

My conscience and lack of sleep will no longer allow me to be quiet and so, the charade must come to an end. I am here to challenge the assumptions and justifications made and offered in the field of engineering schools and engineering schooling. To discuss the dogma that determines our thinking and whether we are justified in carrying on regardless of the arguments that I shall raise in this paper

I shall endeavor to introduce a number of themes in this Philosophical/Engineering paper that are all connected to engineers and engineering awareness. If we look at Epistemology, Ontology and Axiology as the foundation for engineering we shall see a completely different engineer coming out the other side of the equation. Oregon state University has the following statement regarding teaching 'There are three major branches of Philosophy. Each branch focusses on a different aspect and is central to your teaching' The website mentions the three main branches of my paper and why they are so important to teaching; 'Your educational philosophy is your beliefs about why, what and how you teach, whom you teach, and about the nature of learning. It is a set of principles that guides professional action through the events and issues teachers face daily'. That is understanding what your role is as a teacher and as a professional, led by your profession, and not by a subject.

Without using these perspectives to observe and think about the engineer, teaching, the professional, the university and the role of the teacher, I will show that all we're doing is just shooting in the dark without understanding what we are really, actually doing. I shall look at the Engineering environment that a young engineer enters and what the culture of engineering involves, what it means for a young man's future if we continue doing what we do in this manner (I refrain from using the term 'teaching' here). I will show that it is hollow and without insight, it is harmful and undermining for the young engineer and his true role in society. It is detrimental to the environment and lacking in the basics that are seldom addressed. I will finish with a simple argument about how professional we truly are by introducing the professional area and autonomous thinking. Before you refute what I am saying, I should like to quote Aristotle who says 'It is the mark of an educated mind to be able to entertain a thought without accepting it.'

If we teach knowledge, we should have a solid grounding in Epistemology, We should understand what justification and evidence is, and introduce the concept of evidential defeat. Truth and its true meaning, skepticism and empiricism. The Knowing of Knowing has to be an essential part of engineering, because we apply concepts and models constantly to what we are doing without first examining how clean our lenses really are to help us truly see things. We can have knowledge of mathematics, but this knowledge is totally different to the knowledge needed to tackle a complex engineering problem. **Epistemology** is the study of knowledge and how we gain knowledge. If I look at engineering schools, I see that over 70% of all questions in engineering never get beyond the third level of Bloom's taxonomy, which means our students are compelled by us to think in the same way throughout their education. Can we then say that we understand that what we are 'teaching' is true knowledge. Heidegger tells us the following:

"This flight-from-thought is the ground of thoughtlessness. But part of the flight is that man will neither see nor admit it. Man today will even flatly deny this flight from reasoning." (Heidegger)

Thoughtlessness, why? Because our students are not challenged to think reflectively or in any other way except in a calculative manner. This raises the following questions: In what professional environment will our students enter? Will that be purely calculative? If a complex problem has 20 sub-questions are all the sub-questions then calculative questions? When we think about knowledge we think about the following questions also; what is knowledge? Are we teaching real knowledge?. Is a multiple-choice exam a test of pure knowledge? Aren't our questions just a reflection of what happens in the classroom and if we seldom rise above the 3rd level of Bloom's taxonomy, what are we really doing? There are several distinct forms of knowledge; factual, conceptual, procedural and meta-cognitive knowledge and we teach mainly just one. What are the consequences of our actions and are we aware of them?

Heidegger, tells us that we have the potential for thought, but he says

Just as we can grow deaf only because we hear, just as we can grow old only because we were young; so we can grow thought-poor or even thought-less only because man at the core of his being has the capacity to think; has "spirit and reason" and is destined to think.(Heidegger)

Man, of course, has to become aware of the potential of his thinking faculty, and the many shades of thinking that he is capable of. Is this what we awaken in our students? Do we make them aware of this potential that they have naturally? When did we explain the different forms of thinking to them last? Where is epistemology in our curriculum? What are the consequences of it not being there? An important question that you should also address is the following; where they in your curriculum when you were a student? If not, isn't there something dreadfully wrong if thinking as an engineer is not an integral part of the engineer's curriculum?

I think the picture is clear. I think there are very few engineering schools that have even thought about these questions and even fewer that have answered them. The victim is the student and can only be the student. Totally unused potential that will never be completely taken advantage

of except maybe by their future bosses. Do these bosses represent society? Is a company's success the same as society success? Finally, I wonder are engineers the type that will 'flatly deny this flight from reasoning'?

I would now like to move onto **Ontology**, this part of philosophy deals with 'being', I need to discuss the reason for the existence of engineering students. We shall start with the student's learning. Freire states that 'When a person is truly educated, she or he will reflect on the world she or he lives in. This is where liberation comes in.' (**Freire**). Kant believes that understanding who we are and what we are to become needs a special type of thinking; 'Enlightenment is man's release from his self-incurred tutelage. Tutelage is man's inability to make use of his understanding without direction from another. Self-incurred is this tutelage when its cause lies not in lack of reason but in lack of resolution and courage to use it without direction from another.' Students should be independent thinkers at the end of their engineering schooling according to Kant. Are our students thinkers or doers? Can they think autonomously? Are they being directed in their thinking by their company or by their own power of thought? Does the engineering environment demand sound, logical and reflective thinking or will it be o.k. just to teach our students calculative thinking? Isn't this why an engineer exists?

Normally, the tyranny of the majority determines what a decent curriculum is. By determining the make-up of the curriculum they directly influence what is good for an engineer, but what is it based on? Experience? Work? Technology? None of these aspects can give you the answer because we are measuring minds. Minds that can deal with the true engineering environment which can be one of real complexity, a complexity that can never be tackled by calculative thinking alone. It is the reasoning of an engineer that we should be measuring, reasoning based on his insights into complex problems, reasoning to examine the scope and depth of the problem he is faced with. Reasoning that will always give us the best possible answer. Isn't this the true engineering environment? Is this what we should be aiming for? An engineer that does not need anyone to hold his hand, an engineer that Kant himself would be proud of.

Gordon Redding states 'The implication is that the more a society contains individuals who can think for themselves, so as to reach informed judgments and persuade others of them, the greater is the society's capacity to handle the difficult work of adjusting to changing and increasing complexity' A complexity in which our students should be comfortable; my experiences in reading final-year reports show they are not just incapable, but extremely incompetent at understanding the true complexity of the problem they are confronted with. Only through our understanding of who we truly are (**Ontology**) can we get to the truth of what engineering is and what engineering teaching is all about. It has absolutely nothing to do with the product, which is the consequence of what we should be measuring. The analogy of the man who buys a fish and shows his wife what she believes he's caught, although he hasn't the slightest idea of how to fish. It's not about the final product, it is all about knowledge employed along the way.

The seriously tough questions we have to ask if we want to have any value in teaching engineers are the following; Do students become prisoners of their own thinking? Have they been given the tools to escape their calculative thinking? Which classes have given them these

tools? If we hardly ever exceed Bloom's 3rd level in our teaching, when does this higher level of thinking and knowledge become the students own? Can they, through their manner of thinking, ever come to realise the real truth and value of engineering?; What value do these students have for engineering and for society? Can students ever reach anywhere near their true potential through our teaching or are we supplying slaves for the bosses?

We need students who can think autonomously, that we can develop and they can themselves decide where and for whom they want to work. It will always be their choice, but we can rest assured that their choice will be the right one, if they become autonomous thinkers. We should not look at companies or regional tastes to determine what a student learns. Then the following questions arise: If a student is autonomous in his thinking won't he always make the correct choice? Do we measure the autonomy of a student's thinking in the final year at this moment? Or do we measure if the company is happy with the result? Aren't we doing society a great service by creating engineers that have reached their cognitive potential and aren't we creating something special for society? If we answer this question correctly; what is the nature of engineering? Then I think we have a huge duty to answer all the others ones I have posed

The **Ontology of Universities and professionals** is my following point. Redding writes 'Academic freedom is the main expression of openness to understanding relevant external change. At the heart of any such process in most societies is the institution of the university, whose function is to facilitate these processes of continued human and societal evolution **(Redding)** In other words it is the work of universities to interpret the environment's signals and to ensure that our students act in accordance with what is deemed necessary by society. Not to take onboard blindly everything that comes down from a government who cannot possibly have the knowledge of our universities. Should utility be the dominant criteria for our curricula? What values are linked to our criteria? Should corporate values determine what an engineer should look like? Is giving information teaching? Can you create an engineer based on regional preferences? . The word 'teach' implies not only an action but also an achievement, if we only see it as a task, does it matter how we teach as long as we complete our task?

A professional cannot not listen to managers if they believe that they are damaging the teaching or engineering profession. It is our responsibility as professionals and as engineers to protect our professional area. The questions that arise here are the following; Isn't this our duty to determine the forces and dynamics of society and interpret these for our students? Isn't this what defines us as teachers of engineers to determine and protect the environment that the engineer enters so that he can have a complete understanding of his responsibilities in that environment? Can he reach that understanding through his calculative thinking? Don't we as teachers of engineers have to be autonomous thinkers in our function and our roles as teachers of the youth of society? Isn't that our main responsibility? Isn't our job, as professionals, to question our institutes and be critical of any dynamics that will affect or influence our engineering students? Here's a question for you; when did you last have a conflict with your colleagues about the direction of the school curriculum? Can we call ourselves professionals if we sit quietly while our institutes and managers determine what is best for the engineer and the teacher? Should we accept all that comes at us and not even discuss the merits of anything that influences our students? Isn't that our role and our function as both teaching professionals and

as Engineers? Or should we ignore everything except the technical aspect? If the answer is yes, then aren't we just secondary-school level technical people who pass on information to young people? Can you call yourself a teacher if you do not act competently and responsibly in that role? Is it unethical to accept salary if we are being incompetent as teachers of young minds? Is it our responsibility to ensure that our curriculum is properly grounded in our schools and universities and are not based on the whim of the few or the many, but on pure reasoning!

On a different level, the questions that arise should be the following; What value do we have as universities, as centres of knowledge, if we are just doing what the man tells us to do? What value do we have as teachers of engineers who refuse the burden of the teaching profession and just play with our subject? Aren't we just as much slaves as the students we teach? Aren't we also prisoners of our own thinking? Aren't we fooling ourselves by calling ourselves teachers of young minds? When did you last really measure the thinking of a student? I don't mean by giving them multiple choice, but by challenging their thinking in all its aspects.

My third point is **Axiology**, if you want to know about the university you work in, then I suggest you look at who is teaching Ethics, if it is a communications teacher, this proves two things; 1. the engineers themselves do not understand and/or don't want to understand the ethics and morality involved in the work of engineers. Secondly, if ethics is not integrated, although it is a major part of decision making in engineering, can we really say that we understand what engineering really is? Almost every decision an engineer makes is just part of a continuous chain of decisions reaching into other peoples' lives. A student of mine Sparsh asked me a few months ago "Mr xxxxx isn't every engineering problem an ethical problem?". After thinking about it for a minute, thinking about the choices of materials, how we dispose of the material, what the consequences of more automation for society is, every single material choice that we make is at the cost of nature, I had to agree with Sparsh that real engineering in even most simple of environments demands a moral insight that is solid and based on the values of the engineer. Not on the values of the boss. The question arises; What value does a hollow engineer have who has little or no sense of morality? How steady is an engineer who does not understand his own value when it comes to big decisions? How valuable is that same engineer for us as a society? Can society trust such an engineering Cyclops? Aren't we just hollow men who don't want to be enlightened?

My next point is **values**, of course, a wonderful vague term, which most people would never look up in a dictionary; why? Because it is such an everyday word and easy to miss if you do not think about it. Collins' English Dictionary describes values as 'the moral principles and beliefs or accepted standards of a person or social group'. Now if I pose the question 'What are the accepted standards and beliefs of engineering?' I am sure that 98% of teaching engineers have not got a clue what they are. The question then arises; What are the consequences for this ignorance? What does it mean for the young minds we teach? The following questions also have to be answered; "What are the accepted values of the teaching profession?" Is that important? If we cannot answer these two questions, how professional are we really? Can we do any damage as teachers to these young peoples' minds by not being aware of who we are

and what we are? Is it really enough to just teach a technical subject? Isn't that the essence of secondary-level teaching? Can we really call this knowledge? Aren't we just fooling ourselves?

I would like to talk about Hofstede's culture theory and 'the Hollow Men' who I believe are 'engineering teachers', because they may look like teachers, talk like teachers, even do some work that teachers do but if you go to the heart of what they are doing, you will see that they are hollow men who miss the guidance of "Engineering Values" and "Teaching Values". Values tell you who you are, they guide your every decision, they are the steering wheel in your profession. Now I ask you; how can you do anything in teaching if you don't understand that? What guides you? What guides our behavior? What steers us into trouble and keeps us out of trouble?

The next point I would like to introduce is a white rectangle, which I call **the Professional area**, if we as teachers, evaluate a product instead of measuring the thinking behind a product we are dirtying this very white and clean Professional area. There are many ways in which we can soil the professional area, these are; 1. Blaming students 2. Mono-directional teaching 3. Oblivious Teaching 4. Unaware of values 4. Not being jointly responsible for the curriculum 5. Unaware of responsibility to society etc. etc. Each and every point comes from a lack of awareness of what engineering is and what teaching as a profession is. Like blind men, we soil the professional area again and again, and the following question arise; Are we then being incompetent? Do we not create the engineer as prostitute being used and abused by bosses for their own goals, selling themselves and their skills cheaply, without ever debating whether the boss is the one to be served? Do we not undermine the role and importance of engineering again and again if we know not what we do? How professional are we really?

Let us now talk about what we should be trying to achieve. Autonomous thinking, this is what we should be doing according to Horvath; discussing what students should be capable of doing; 'Reflection, self-reflection, evaluation and self-evaluation best support effective learning if their results are relevant to the learning process. Thus their success depends to a large extent on the students' metacognitive knowledge, that is, the knowledge possessed by the students about themselves as learners and the learning process.' Independent, reflective, metacognitive thinkers who we can trust in the roles we give them as a society. We can trust them because they understand what an engineer is, they understand who they are, they are aware of the consequences of their work and the importance of the decisions they make. They are responsible for their environments, they are true engineers

To conclude, there is light at the end of the tunnel. That light is indeed the light of the real world, let us leave the caves that we have been inhabiting for years, and go out into the light of awareness and by becoming aware, we truly become what we have been playing at for the past years!

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